

Photochemistry of *vic*-diols in the presence of benzoyl peroxide and *N*-bromosuccinimide

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Various vicinal diols have been irradiated in the presence of benzoyl peroxide and *N*-bromosuccinimide. Oxidation products are predominating wherever hydrogens at the carbon carrying hydroxyl groups are available. In the case of tertiary hydroxyl groups, oxidative retrodimerisation products are predominant.

Photolysis of secondary aromatic alcohols has been reported by Balsells and Frasca¹ leading to poor yields (<13%) of carbonyl compounds. In order to improve the yields, light-induced reactions^{2,3} have been studied. Literature records some instances of inorganic material being used for oxidation of *vic*-diols in thermal reactions⁴. Thus it was thought worthwhile to study photolysis of *vic*-diols in the presence of benzoyl peroxide and *N*-bromosuccinimide (NBS).

meso-1,2-Diphenyl-1,2-ethanediol (1), *meso*-1,2-di(4-methoxyphenyl)-1,2-ethanediol (2), *meso*-2,3-diphenyl-2,3-butanediol (3) and benzopinacol (4) showed no dark reaction with benzoyl peroxide in dichloromethane. However, compound 1 when irradiated in the presence of benzoyl peroxide in dichloromethane for 14 h yielded an unidentified product (1.2%), benzil (5, 25.1%), benzaldehyde (17.1%), the unreacted diol (28.4%) and benzoic acid (75.8%) after column chromatography of the photolysate. The remainder was a polymeric product and its structure could not be assigned. Compound 2 when irradiated in dichloromethane in the presence of benzoyl peroxide for 1 h gave an unidentified product (4.5%), anisil (6, 30%), *p*-anisaldehyde (32.1%) and anisic acid (12.2%). Benzoic acid was obtained in 92.0% yield alongwith a polymeric product (13.6%). Compound 3 on irradiation in the presence of benzoyl peroxide in dichloromethane for 13 h gave acetophenone (7, 10.1%) and benzoic acid (20.2%). In this case, the starting diol (75%) and benzoyl peroxide (71.3%) were also recovered alongwith a tarry material (1.5%). It gave two more unidentified fractions in 1.0 and 1.2% yields respectively, but our attempts to identify these products failed. When benzopinacol (4) was irradiated in the presence of benzoyl peroxide for 2 h, benzophenone (20.1%) was formed alongwith an unidentified product (1.1%) preceded by the starting diol (62.8%), benzoyl peroxide (50.4%), benzoic acid (26.1%) and a polymeric product (5.5%). One more unidentified compound (1.9%) was also formed.

It was then thought worthwhile to study the photolysis of the diols in presence of *N*-bromosuccinimide. Compound 1 was subjected to dark reaction in the presence of *N*-bromosuccinimide in dichloromethane when benzil (5) was formed in 1% yield after 4 h which increased to 5% after 24 h. However, on irradiation in the presence of *N*-bromosuccinimide in dichloromethane for 10 min, 29.2% yield of 5 was obtained. It was accompanied by benzaldehyde (2.9%), benzoin (8, 36.0%) and benzoic acid (3.7%). The rest was a polymeric product which could not be identified. Compound 2 in the presence of *N*-bromosuccinimide in dichloromethane on being kept in diffused sunlight at room temperature for 30 min gave anisil (6, 2%). After 24 h, the yield of anisil increased to 12% and *p*-anisaldehyde (5%) was also formed. However, compound 2 on being irradiated for 30 min in the presence of *N*-bromosuccinimide in dichloromethane gave *p*-anisil (20.3%) and *p*-anisaldehyde (10.1%). *p*-Anisic acid was also isolated in 54.2% yield and the rest was an unidentified polymeric product. The structure of *p*-anisil was established by its 90 MHz nmr spectrum⁵ and that of *p*-anisic acid by its mass and nmr spectrum⁵. Exposure of compound 3 to diffused sunlight for 10 min led to the formation of 5% of the products. However, the conversion was quantitative when irradiated for 10 min in dichloromethane leading to the formation of acetophenone (7, 38.2%), 2,3-diphenyl-1,3-butadiene (9, 2.4%), phenacyl bromide (10, 21.5%) and the starting diol (3, 29.4%). An unidentified polymeric product (7.1%) was also obtained. The structure of the diene was confirmed by its nmr spectrum which was identical with that reported in literature⁶. The structure of phenacyl bromide was also confirmed by its nmr spectrum⁵.

Benzopinacol (4) on being kept in the presence of *N*-bromosuccinimide in dichloromethane in the dark at room temperature showed no noticeable change. However, on being irradiated for 30 min in the presence of *N*-

